

Smithereens of Dental Treatment Myths Busting It and Purveying Facts Among Indian Population – A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess how much taboos and myths among people are the reasons for neglect towards dental treatment.

Material & Methods: A cross-sectional questionnaire study carried out among patients visiting the outpatient department of a dental hospital in Nagpur, Vidarbha, Maharashtra. A self-administered validated questionnaire was used to collect data regarding the reasons for patients to neglect dental treatment. The Data was analyzed using Statistical package for social sciences software.

Results: Out of 152 outpatients only 16(10.7%) had come for a general checkup of the teeth; rest 136 (89.3%) had some or the other issues with their teeth but had neglected it for the following reasons- out of these 136, 103 (75.7%) of the patients reported that they were having some myth about dental treatments and feared not to report their problem until it was an extremely unbearable.

Conclusion: Even in this 21st century in a well-developed metro city like Nagpur Maharashtra more than three-fourth of people believed visit for a dental treatment would hamper their general health, and had myths regarding dental treatments, efforts should be directed towards removal of these myths from patient's mind; in which media has to play a major role for a better future of this country.

KEYWORDS: myths, taboos, dental treatment.

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INTRODUCTION

Presence of oral diseases worldwide is unsurprisingly high which affects a huge number of the world's total population. Malnutrition among the vulnerable and poor strata of people also share the brunt of oral diseases. A high prevalence of illiteracy their knowledge and awareness about how important oral health is to general health is drastically negligible. Oral health undoubtedly is vital part which often gets neglected to procure health and well-being overall. Dental caries, periodontitis and other oral diseases contribute to global health issues. ^[1]

In most of the developing countries including India, Family life, birth, childrearing, and death are often based on the culture or customs that prevail in a society, the recognition of illness and care-seeking practices around health or medical/dental conditions. These beliefs and practices can be barriers or help accessing health care services. ^[2] A similar scenario is seen vastly in relation to dental aspect.

Culture is often defined as "training and refinement of mind, tastes and manners, the condition of being thus trained and refined- *The Oxford Dictionary*." ^[1] Oxford University Press (<http://www.oed.com>) English

<http://www.oed.com/viewdictionaryentry/Entry/111251> Many myths and taboos too do prevail in these cultural or social beliefs.

A Myth can be defined as "A traditional story, especially one concerning the early history of the people or explaining a natural or social phenomenon, and typically involving supernatural beings or events."

Taboos are defined as "A strong social prohibition against words, actions, objects that are considered offensive for the society." ^[3]

A key element of social context is the patterned process of people making sense of their world, and the (conscious and unconscious) assumptions, expectations, and practices they call upon to do so ^[2,3], some of which can be factitious while others being fictitious.

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With approximately 30,000 dentists graduating each year from a staggering 310 plus dental colleges in India as on date (*as per Dental Council of India official Website*); curbing dental related issues still remain a challenge to be taken Even the most basic diseases like Dental Caries which is reported 31.5% to 89% among various studies.^[4,5] children and young adults & Periodontal Disease burden among adults being more than 90%^[6,7] it becomes a robust task for this huge number of workforce.

There are innumerable reasons of the above said one of the important reason in not being able to curb dental disease is MYTHS/TABOOS related to dental problems. As there is minimal literature published in this regards this study was conducted to know the level of taboos and myths among people being a reasons for neglect towards dental treatment.

The aim of the present study was to assess how much taboos and/ myths among people persists being the reason for neglect towards dental treatment with an objective of knowing about current trends in reasons for dental neglect among population visiting the outpatient department with the help of a structured questionnaire.

MATERIALS & METHODS

A cross sectional survey study was done to evaluate and assess myths prevailing in dentistry. A pilot tested questionnaire was used in the present study and also for sample size determination which would be apt for the study.

With the help of pilot study on 30 subjects, minor changes in the questionnaire were made for its external validity and a final questionnaire was prepared and printed both in English and the local language (marathi); consisting of 2 parts to assess a general attitude of the patient in 1st part including their demographic details; and myths if any was patients reason for dental neglect.

Out-patients visiting the college in the month of December 2024 and January 2025 were taken with a systematic random sampling method; every 4th patient visiting the dental college in 4 randomly selected weeks (1st & 4th in December and 3rd and 4th in January) on 4 randomly selected days (Tuesday Thursday Friday & Saturday in 2nd week; Monday Wednesday Friday & Saturday in 4th week of December 2024; Monday Tuesday Wednesday & Thursday in 2nd week and Monday Wednesday Friday & Saturday in 4th week of January 2025) were taken into the study to come to the pre-calculated sample size of 146. In an attempt to negate any sampling bias 5% was added up to this and a final total of 152 were taken in the study.

The inclusion criteria were – Only new OPD patients were taken in the study, those who readily & willingly agreed to take part in the study, finally only those sheets that were fully completed questionnaire were taken in consideration for the study. Patients who were coming for recall treatment, patients with 1 or more than 1 exposure to any dental treatment anywhere were excluded from the study

As there was no intervention required the ethical clearance was obtained without much hindrances prior to beginning of the study from the institutions ethical review committee.

Patients were informed about the study in brief and were assured for the confidentiality of their answers followed by obtaining an informed consent from the patients. The completed questionnaires were collected back and were put for statistical analysis, as only qualitative variables were assessed only nonparametric tests chi square test & spearman's correlation test were used for analysis in the study and the probability value was set it <0.05 for the study.

Post completion of the study those participated in the study were called and Facts about the taboos and myths given as hard copy for their motivation and knowledge improvement. These were also circulated in general in the OPD to all walk in patients as well

RESULTS

Among 152 outpatients only 16(10.7%) had come for a general checkup of the teeth; rest 136 (89.3%) had some oral problem but had neglected it. (Chart 1)

Out of a total of 152 patients 93 were males and 59 were females patients.(Chart 2)

There was no statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$) suggesting both males and females had equal myths regarding neglect of dental treatment.

Among the patients under study 103 (67.7%) of the patients reported that they were having some myth about dental treatments and hence had not reported their problem until it was an extremely unbearable condition. The rest 49 (32.3%) people didn't come to the hospital - stated lack of time prior to this visit. (Chart 3)

Spearman's correlation test revealed a p value of <0.05($p 0.03$) suggesting a clear correlation between myths and dental neglect.

A few most common myths encountered during the study were

Myth 1 – if I do not have any dental pain, I feel regular dental visits are not necessary. 79(51.9%)

Myth 2 – I feel once a tooth has a filling or cap additional care is no longer needed. 56(36.8%)

Myth 3 – I feel brushing is sufficient enough to keep teeth clean. 98(64.5%)

Myth 4 – I feel removing deposits/tartar from teeth by dentist will loosen my teeth 65(42.7%)

Myth 5 – my parents didn't have any problem/didn't visit any dentist so even I won't have any problem in teeth and I don't need to visit a dentist. 77(50.7%)

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Myth 6 – I feel brushing with salt will remove stains and problems and whiten the teeth. 48(31.6%)

Myth 7 – I feel if I get my teeth removed it will affect my eyesight. 89(58.6%)

Myth 8 – I feel only the sugar in sweets and chocolates/desserts is bad for teeth. 96 (63.1%)

Myth 9 – I feel only cause of tooth problem is poor brushing so if I brush properly I don't need to visit a dentist 73(48%)

Myth 10 – I feel everybody needs false teeth/ dentures when they get older 87(57.2%).

(Graph 4 & 5 No. of people having individual myths and Percentage distribution.)

The results obtained from the study suggest that even in today's modern world substantial amount of myths and taboos persists in the society. The current myths prevailing in the society have been enumerated from this study. These myths which prevail not only puts the patients on back foot for not approaching health services available but also increases the disease burden of the society hand in hand.

DISCUSSION

The rampancy of myths about dental treatment appeared to be alarmingly high even today when we have crossed nearly a quarter of 21st century, more than 3/4th of people believed- visit for a dental treatment would hamper their general health, and had myths regarding dental treatment. This may be as a result of fairly poor early health seeking behavior early in childhood through adulthood which in turn had obvious poor compliance with treatment.

The present study was conducted to assess the prevailing myths and taboos related to dentistry, which makes the patient neglect dental care until it becomes completely unbearable for the patient.

Most of the blogs available on the web put up by owners and dentists of various clinics in India were taken to generate the questionnaire which was further pilot tested on a group of 30 out patients, after the pilot study a final questionnaire was chalked down which gave a validated 2 part self-administered questionnaire and was the main tool of the study.

This questionnaire was typed in English language and local language for patient comfort and compliance with it; the first part had 5 questions assessing the general attitude of the patient towards dental treatment, and the second part assessing the Myths which prevail in the community which had 10 most commonly encountered myths in undergoing dental treatment.

As all the questions were taken from the blogs available on the net and most common ones were only included in the present study the findings of current study are similar to those available on the blogs.

A study done in turkey quoted that dental procedures can lead to miscellaneous ophthalmic complications possibly due to the close proximity of the anatomic structures. Retinal arterial occlusion is a rare but serious cause of permanent visual loss among these dental procedures where the exact pathologic mechanism is still obscure. One of the reasons could be the neglect of dental treatment at early stages and need for more intensive dental care. [8]

A Malaysian paper states infection in the tooth socket and extending to orbital cavity through para-nasal sinuses is rare but it can result significant morbidity and mortality. Optic neuropathy, visual loss and multiple cranial nerve palsy with eye structures motility impairment are the hallmark of orbital apex syndrome. [9] Neglecting dental treatment at an incipient stage due to myth like extraction of upper teeth impacts eyesight might initiate the cascade effect of spread of infection from early stage to more vital structures like orbital cavity.

Heart attack and stroke risk may rise in the month following invasive dental treatments such as tooth extractions, and the risk returns to normal levels within six months, according to the study published in *Annals of Internal Medicine*.

On the contrary WHO states - the compartmentalization involved in viewing the mouth separately from the rest of the body must cease because oral health affects general health by causing considerable pain and suffering and by changing what people eat, their speech and their quality of life and well-being. Oral health also has an effect on other chronic diseases. By integrating oral health into strategies for promoting general health and by assessing oral needs in socio-dental ways, health planners can greatly enhance both general and oral health. [10,11]

As such negative blogs, articles prevail and with the use of internet expanding voluminously day by day access to such material to general public is easier, which may be one of the causes creating myths among people and neglecting dental treatment.

There are very minimal numbers of such studies/ literature available this study could be taken as a baseline measure for such studies in future. Limitation of time and resources could be possible shortcomings in the present study, hence further studies targeting not only out patients of a college but also general populations could be taken into consideration.

Hard copies in the form of printed Facts regarding prevailing myths were circulated among general population, all the OPD patients post study for 2 months on regular basis and to the target population in their follow up visits and those who didn't report on their follow up, these pamphlets were mailed to their given addresses with a vision of motivating masses not to neglect dental treatment

CONCLUSION

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Based on the responses of patients it was conclusive that more than 2/3rd population had myths which became the reasons for neglect of Dental treatment. These people when reported to the dental college were already had advanced stages of diseases.

Myths and misconceptions surrounding dental treatments and traditional practices were most prevalent among uneducated and older populations. Limited education and a lack of accessible information were identified as major obstacles, significantly hindering the use of dental services.

To overcome the large burden of oral issues prevailing in our country, Efforts should be directed towards removal of these myths from patient's mind starting from the grass root level; by educating children in their primary school itself regarding the importance of oral health for general health as oral health is an integral part of General health.

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